

Notes

Iron(III) Complexes of some Azodyes derived from Antipyrine

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Many azo compounds were found to give stable complexes with transition metals. In this paper we report the preparation and characterisation of a few iron(III) complexes of three ligands, 1-phenyl-2,3-dimethyl-4-(2-hydroxynaphthylazo)-5-pyrazolone (naphthylazoantipyrine, NAAP), 1-phenyl-2,3-dimethyl-4-(2,4-dihydroxyphenylazo)-5-pyrazolone (resorcinolazo antipyrine, RAAP) and 1-phenyl-2,3-dimethyl-4-(2-hydroxy-4-methylphenylazo)-5-pyrazolone (cresol azoantipyrine, CAAP).

around 1460 cm^{-1} ($\text{N}=\text{N}$) in the spectra of the ligands shifted to around 1430 cm^{-1} in the spectra of the complexes, showing the participation of the azo-nitrogen in the coordination. Thus all the ligands are found to be terdentate monovalent in nature. The analytical data of the complexes also confirm this.

Experimental

The ligands were prepared by the reported method¹. The iron(III) complexes were prepared by refluxing the metal salts (0.005 mol) with a methanol solution (0.01 mol) of the ligands for 3 h. The resulting complexes were washed with water followed by benzene (A.R.) and dried under reduced pressure over P_2O_5 .

The anions were estimated by standard methods². Perchlorate was estimated by Kurz method³. Iron in perchlorate complexes was estimated gravimetrically⁴. The magnetic susceptibility at room temperature was measured on a Gouy balance. The molar conductance (in nitrobenzene and acetonitrile) was measured using an ELICO CM 82 conductivity meter. IR spectra were recorded on a Beckman IR 20A spectrophotometer and electronic spectra on a Shimadzu UV 200 spectrophotometer.

Results and Discussion

The analytical data of the compounds are presented in Table 1. The molar conductance values of the complexes in nitrobenzene (19–26 $\Omega^{-1} \text{cm}^2 \text{mol}^{-1}$) and acetonitrile (126–160 $\Omega^{-1} \text{cm}^2 \text{mol}^{-1}$) show that the complexes are 1:1 electrolytes.

IR spectra of the ligands show a broad band of medium intensity around 2900 cm^{-1} assignable to hydrogen bonded OH group⁵. This band is absent in the spectra of all the complexes. This suggests that the ligand reacts with the metal ion with the elimination of the replaceable hydrogen. The IR bands in the ligands around 1660 cm^{-1} ($\text{C}=\text{O}$) shifted to lower frequency by 30–60 cm^{-1} in the spectra of all the complexes showing the involvement of $\text{C}=\text{O}$ oxygen in coordination. A band

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL DATA OF COMPLEXES

Compd.	Colour	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd)	
		Metal	% Anion
$\text{Fe}(\text{NAAP})_2\text{Cl}$	Black	7.1 (7.5)	5.5 (4.7)
$\text{Fe}(\text{NAAP})_2\text{Br}$	Dark brown	7.1 (6.5)	8.5 (9.3)
$\text{Fe}(\text{NAAP})_2\text{ClO}_4$	Black	7.0 (6.3)	10.5 (11.4)
$\text{Fe}(\text{NAAP})_2\text{SO}_4/2$	Black	6.6 (6.7)	5.2 (5.8)
$\text{Fe}(\text{RAAP})_2\text{Cl}$	Black	8.4 (7.5)	5.4 (4.7)
$\text{Fe}(\text{RAAP})_2\text{Br}$	Black	8.0 (7.0)	11.2 (10.0)
$\text{Fe}(\text{RAAP})_2\text{ClO}_4$	Black	7.0 (6.8)	13.8 (14.1)
$\text{Fe}(\text{RAAP})_2\text{SO}_4/2$	Black	8.0 (7.4)	5.3 (4.7)
$\text{Fe}(\text{CAAP})_2\text{Cl}$	Brown	7.8 (7.3)	4.9 (4.7)
$\text{Fe}(\text{CAAP})_2\text{Br}$	Brown	7.5 (7.1)	9.8 (10.2)
$\text{Fe}(\text{CAAP})_2\text{ClO}_4$	Dark brown	7.1 (6.9)	11.1 (12.4)
$\text{Fe}(\text{CAAP})_2\text{SO}_4/2$	Brown	6.2 (7.4)	5.4 (6.4)

The electronic spectra of the three ligands are similar. All of them have a band around 43470 cm^{-1} attributed to the $\pi^* \leftarrow \pi$ transition and another at 22720 cm^{-1} due to the $\pi^* \leftarrow n$ transition. In the spectra of all the complexes, the $\pi^* \leftarrow n$ transition was found blue-shifted to 26310 cm^{-1} . This suggests the involvement of the carbonyl group in the complex formation. The spectra of all the complexes exhibit low intensity broad bands in the region 16660–20000 cm^{-1} which are due to the $d-d$ transition. For a high-spin octahedral iron complex, the expected μ_{eff} value is 5.9 B.M.⁶. The lower values (5.0–5.4 B.M.) in the complexes indicate metal-metal interaction.

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